

Development of a P2D-based model for battery swelling prediction under mechanical constraints

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HIGHLIGHTS

- A P2D-based model predicts battery swelling under mechanical constraints.
- Pressure-dependent parameters capture constrained swelling behavior.
- Swelling prediction is enabled without real-time sensors during operation.

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ABSTRACT

Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) for electric vehicles are typically assembled into modules with mechanical constraints that exert external pressure on individual cells to improve stability and performance. During operation, battery swelling behavior under mechanical constraint generates external pressure fluctuation that can lead to structural degradation, including electrode cracking, separator deformation, and accelerated side reactions. This ultimately increases the risk of safety issues such as internal short circuits and thermal runaway. While existing battery simulation models provide insights into the mechanisms of battery swelling, many overlook the influence of external mechanical pressure. However, these effects should not be overlooked, as they impact the behavior of battery swelling. In this study, we present a pseudo-two-dimensional (P2D) model which integrates lithium ion transport dynamics with pressure-dependent parameters to enable swelling prediction of LIBs under mechanical constraints without requiring real-time sensors during operation. We found that the model predicts cell thickness changes during 1C discharge at 0.164 MPa with a mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) of 6.87% compared to experimental results. These findings bridge the gap in predicting changes in cell thickness under mechanical constraints. The approach in our study is crucial for the safety assessment of mechanically constrained battery systems.

1. Introduction

Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) have become the primary rechargeable energy storage technology for electric vehicles (EVs) due to their excellent energy density and cycle performance [1,2]. In practical applications, LIBs are assembled into modules with mechanical constraints that exert external pressure on individual cells [3,4]. During operation, LIBs undergo volumetric expansion through cycling. This expansion causes both reversible and irreversible thickness variations, known as

battery swelling, which results in increased external mechanical pressure [5,6]. This increased mechanical pressure can lead to structural degradation, including electrode cracking, separator deformation, and accelerated side reactions, ultimately increasing safety risks such as internal short circuits and thermal runaway [7–11]. Understanding the interplay between battery swelling and external mechanical constraints is therefore critical for predicting mechanical behavior, maintaining structural integrity, and developing safer battery systems for real-world applications over the entire lifecycle.

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LIBs swelling occurs continuously throughout the battery lifecycle and can be categorized into reversible [3,6,12] and irreversible mechanisms [13–15]. Reversible swelling stems from electrode volume changes during lithium intercalation, deintercalation, alloying, and conversion processes [13,16–18]. Irreversible swelling results from side reactions including for example solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) layer growth, gas evolution, plastic deformation, and cumulative mechanical damage [19–21]. In automotive applications, LIBs are assembled into modules or cell-to-pack configurations with structural housings designed to manage both external loads and internal mechanical stresses. These housings incorporate optimized preload forces to enhance battery performance, but this initial compression directly affects pressure accumulation throughout the operational lifetime [22, 23]. Under constrained conditions, LIBs swelling progressively increases housing pressure during cycling, potentially degrading performance and reducing cycle life [24,25]. It is therefore essential to predict external pressure and battery swelling during operation for performance and safety assessment. However, pressure and displacement sensors have not yet been widely implemented in battery systems due to high costs and integration complexity [26].

Researchers utilize battery modelling and simulation as powerful tools for enhancing LIBs design, optimizing operating conditions, and gaining insights into internal processes [27–33]. The foundational electrochemical-based LIBs models were developed by Newman and co-workers, applying concentrated solution and porous electrode theories to simulate Li^+ concentration in electrodes during galvanostatic charge and discharge [34,35]. Subsequent modelling advances have incorporated mechanical phenomena to better understand LIB degradation mechanisms across multiple length scales, from particle-to electrode-level and full-cell representations [36]. At the microscopic scale, electrochemical-mechanical coupled models have been developed to investigate stress generation, crack formation, and fracture propagation within individual active particles during lithiation/de-lithiation cycles [37,38]. Christensen and Newman established a mathematical model correlating Li^+ concentration with particle stress and strain [39], while Zhang et al. conducted numerical simulations to quantify intercalation-induced stress and strain from concentration gradients [40]. A second stream of modelling effort focuses on aging-oriented electro-mechanical coupling, where mechanical degradation mechanisms such as SEI growth [41], active material loss [42], and particle cracking [43] are linked to long-term electrochemical performance evolution. At the macroscopic scale, electrode and cell-level models capture dimensional changes, with Rieger et al. proposing a method to predict cell thickness change during reversible swelling by linking particle-level strain to cell expansion [13,44]. These models effectively capture reversible and irreversible swelling due to electrode expansion, lithium intercalation, and material degradation. In parallel, a number of experimental studies have demonstrated that externally applied pressure measurably alters electrode porosity, ionic transport resistance, and electrochemical performance [45–47]. Cannarella et al. showed that higher stress may cause higher rates of capacity fade through cycleable lithium loss [4]. Müller et al. reported that pressure could increase the ionic pore resistance of graphite anodes and NMC cathodes through compression-induced reductions in porosity and tortuosity [48,49]. Schabenberger et al. found higher pressure peaks during compression lead to greater initial deterioration of rate capability [50]. While recent studies have characterized the impact of external pressure on cell behavior, existing electro-mechanical models generally focus on either internal stress evolution or long-term aging kinetics. These frameworks typically lack the pressure-dependent parameters necessary to predict thickness variations under mechanical constraint. This remains a significant oversight, as external pressure is a primary determinant of swelling dynamics in constrained systems, yet it is rarely coupled directly with transport properties in current predictive models [29,30].

To address this gap, the present study develops a mechanical swelling model based on the pseudo-two-dimensional (P2D) approach.

This model integrates lithium ion (Li^+) transport dynamics with pressure-dependent parameters in order to predict changes in cell thickness for reversible swelling under external mechanical constraints. The modelling framework operates in two phases: calibration and prediction. During the calibration phase, displacement and pressure sensors are required for initial model parameterization. Once calibrated, the model enables prediction of reversible cell thickness changes without the need for real-time pressure or displacement measurements. The model thus reduces sensor requirements for swelling monitoring during operation. The P2D framework is selected to establish the foundational coupling between external mechanical pressure and swelling behavior. The P2D approach offers a practical balance between physical fidelity and computational efficiency, enabling systematic validation of the pressure-swelling coupling mechanism. The main goal is to address current modelling gaps by incorporating the effects of external pressure into established theoretical frameworks. This will be achieved by integrating P2D modelling for Li^+ transport with macroscopic battery swelling mechanisms. We implement the model in PyBaMM (Python Battery Mathematical Modelling), an open-source Python library for battery modelling, by using pure Python code to facilitate accessible simulations without specialized software or physical sensors [41,51,52]. This approach enables the prediction of reversible swelling behavior in batteries under mechanical constraints, thereby advancing the capabilities of safety assessments for real-world applications. Furthermore, it paves the way for subsequent research focused on real-time force monitoring technologies. It should be noted that this study is based on a single battery cell, whereas future investigations will extend to stack-level analysis.

2. Method

The modelling framework adopts a multiscale approach to predict reversible swelling in LIBs, linking electrochemical processes to mechanical swelling under varying external pressures, as shown in Fig. 1. Beginning with a pseudo-two-dimensional (P2D) electrochemical model at the particle level, it resolves lithium-ion Li^+ concentration changes during discharge. These local variations are upscaled to the electrode level, driving volumetric expansion in the porous structure, and ultimately to the cell level, where the integrated effects quantify overall cell thickness change. Central to this linkage is the partial molar volume Ω which is a thermodynamic property quantifying the volumetric change when intercalating species are inserted into a host material. In LIBs, it describes the effect of how Li^+ insertion affects the volume of electrode materials such as graphite anodes and transition metal oxide cathodes [53]. In this study, the partial molar volume $\Omega_{(c,P)}$ is treated as a function of both Li^+ concentration c and external pressure P . This dependency captures the coupled electrochemical-mechanical interactions within the cell, reflecting how lithium intercalation-induced volume changes are influenced by compressive constraints [53–56]. In this study, the constrained swelling behavior of the electrode under applied pressure is attributed to the variation in $\Omega_{(c,P)}$, which governs the volumetric response of the active material during lithium insertion and extraction.

At the particle level, the P2D model simulates Li^+ intercalation by resolving radial concentration gradients c within active material particles in both electrodes during cycling. These local concentration profiles, combined with the concentration- and pressure-dependent partial molar volume $\Omega_{(c,P)}$, inform the integrated volumetric expansion per particle $\Delta V_{particle}$, given by Equation (1) [13].

$$\Delta V_{particle} = \int_{c_0}^{c_n} \Omega_{(c,P)} dc_{(P)} \quad (1)$$

A schematic of the P2D model, as shown in Fig. 2, provides a rigorous framework for simulating the electrochemical behavior of a lithium-ion cell [57]. The cell is represented as a one-dimensional (1D) structure

Fig. 1. Principle of the model framework.

Fig. 2. Schematic of a P2D model.

along the x -coordinate, which is oriented perpendicular to the current collector. This 1D domain encompasses three distinct regions: the anode, the separator, and the cathode, with a respective thickness of L_n , L_s , and L_p . The total cell thickness is defined as $L = L_n + L_s + L_p$. Spatial uniformity is assumed in the y - and z -directions parallel to the current collector, enabling a simplified 1D representation of the cell. Within the P2D framework, key electrochemical processes are modelled across two different spatial scales. At the macroscopic scale, along the x -coordinate, the model describes the distribution of electrical potential in the solid electrodes and the electrolyte, as well as the transport of Li^+ through the electrolyte phase. At the microscopic scale, Li^+ transport within the active material of the electrodes is modelled as diffusion within a 1D spherical particle, parameterized by the radial coordinate. This dual-scale approach couples the cell-level dynamics in the x -direction with particle-level diffusion processes in the r -direction, providing a comprehensive description of the electrochemical interactions that determine the performance of lithium-ion batteries.

The P2D model is governed by a set of coupled partial differential equations that describe the electrochemical processes within a lithium-ion cell. As detailed in Table 1, these governing equations encompass the conservation of mass and charge transport in both the electrolyte and solid phases, as well as the kinetics of electrochemical reactions at the electrode-electrolyte interfaces. A full description of the equations, including their derivation and assumptions, can be found in the literature [34,35,58].

Through integration of volumetric expansions of individual active material particles, these particle-level effects scale to the electrode level swelling, where intercalation-induced volume changes result in electrode thickness change $dL_{(P)}$ within the layered architecture [13,44]. As detailed in Equation (2), the electrode swelling equation translates this integrated particle expansion to the electrode domain by incorporating both the pressure-dependent active material volume fraction $\varepsilon_{s,(P)}$ and the pressure-dependent electrode thickness $L_{(P)}$.

$$dL_{(P)} = \varepsilon_{s,(P)} * L_{(P)} * \int_{c_0}^{c_n} \Omega_{(c,P)} dc_{(P)} \quad (2)$$

Finally, at the cell scale, the electrode-level swelling is aggregated across stacked layers n to compute the cell thickness change $dt_{(P)}$ as shown in Equation (3). In our study, we focus on the intercalation effect as the main contributor to battery swelling. Our research indicates that the intercalation-induced swelling is more pronounced in the anode than in the cathode, with the anode exhibiting greater thickness changes

Table 1
Governing equations of the electrochemical P2D model.

Domain	Equation	Boundary condition
Solid phase, mass balance	$\frac{\partial c_s}{\partial t} = \frac{D_s^{eff}}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial c_s}{\partial r} \right)$	$\frac{\partial c_s}{\partial r} \Big _{r=0} = 0, D_s^{eff} \frac{\partial c_s}{\partial r} \Big _{r=R} = -\frac{j^{Li}}{a_s F}$
Solid phase, state of charge	$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\sigma^{eff} \frac{\partial \phi_s}{\partial x} \right) = j^{Li}$	$\sigma^{eff} \frac{\partial \phi_s}{\partial x} \Big _{x=0} = \sigma^{eff} \frac{\partial \phi_s}{\partial x} \Big _{x=L} = I,$ $\sigma^{eff} \frac{\partial \phi_s}{\partial x} \Big _{x=L_n} = \sigma^{eff} \frac{\partial \phi_s}{\partial x} \Big _{x=L_n+L_s} = 0$
Liquid phase, mass balance	$\varepsilon_e \frac{\partial c_e}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(D_e^{eff} \frac{\partial c_e}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{1-t_+}{F} j^{Li}$	$\frac{\partial c_e}{\partial x} \Big _{x=0} = \frac{\partial c_e}{\partial x} \Big _{x=L} = 0$
Liquid phase, state of charge	$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\kappa^{eff} \frac{\partial \phi_e}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\kappa_D^{eff} \frac{\partial \ln c_e}{\partial x} \right) + j^{Li} = 0$	$\frac{\partial \phi_e}{\partial x} \Big _{x=0} = \frac{\partial \phi_e}{\partial x} \Big _{x=L} = 0$
Butler-Volmer kinetic	$j^{Li} = 2a_s i_0 \sinh \left(\frac{0.5F}{RT} \eta \right),$ $i_0 = k \sqrt{c_e (c_{s,max} - c_{s,surf}) c_{s,surf}}$	

under repeated charge-discharge cycles [24,30]. Consequently, we attribute all observed thickness variations during cycling exclusively to the anode, thereby simplifying the model by neglecting contributions from the cathode. To further streamline the study and reduce complexity, we have chosen to disregard the effect of thermal expansion. The constrained swelling model provides a foundational framework for analyzing variations in battery thickness under mechanical constraints. The model is used to simulate the battery thickness changes $dt_{(P)}$ under constrained conditions, where the electrode assembly is subject to external forces that limit free expansion. Accounting for these dependencies enables the model to predict reversible swelling behavior in detail and provide insights into how mechanical constraints influence the structural integrity and performance of the battery.

$$dt_{(P)} = n^* \varepsilon_{s,(P)} * L_{(P)} * \int_{c_0}^{c_n} \Omega_{(c,P)} dc_{(P)} \quad (3)$$

As shown in Equation (3), active material fraction $\varepsilon_{s,(P)}$, negative electrode single layer thickness $L_{(P)}$, negative electrode concentration $c_{(P)}$, and cell thickness change $dt_{(P)}$ in the constrained state are needed to calculate the equation-derived partial molar volume $\Omega_{(c,P)}$.

2.1. Pressure-dependent mechanical properties of electrodes

Pressure dependency of active material fraction $\varepsilon_{s,(P)}$

In our study, we made two assumptions regarding the mechanical properties of the porous electrode [44]. The first assumption is that the electrode comprises both a porous material and an active material in the calculation. The second assumption states when external pressure P_1 is applied, only the pore volume V_{pore} undergoes compression while the active material volume $V_{active\ material,P_0}$ remains unchanged [15,29,59]. The schematic of how the porous electrode is compressed by external pressure is shown in Fig. 3. The subscript P_0 denotes the state without external pressure, while P_1 indicates the state under external pressure P_1 .

The initial active material fraction without external pressure influence ε_{s,P_0} , in an electrode is defined as the ratio of the active material volume $V_{active\ material,P_0}$, to the total electrode volume $V_{electrode,P_0}$, as shown in Equation (4). Following compression, the active material fraction ε_{s,P_1} is recalculated by dividing the active material volume $V_{active\ material,P_0}$ by the compressed electrode volume $V_{electrode,P_1}$, as shown in Equation (5). The compressed electrode volume $V_{electrode,P_1}$ is determined by dividing the original electrode volume $V_{electrode,P_0}$ by the change in pore volume V_{pore} , denoted as $\Delta V_{pore,P_1}$. The value of $\Delta V_{pore,P_1}$ is computed by multiplying the original electrode volume $V_{electrode,P_0}$ by the strain ε_{P_1} induced during compression. The strain ε_{P_1} is derived by dividing the applied compressive stress P_1 by the compression modulus E_{s,P_1} of the electrode material. These relationships provide a consistent framework for quantifying the impact of compression on the electrode's active material fraction ε_{s,P_1} .

$$\varepsilon_{s,P_0} = \frac{V_{active\ material,P_0}}{V_{electrode,P_0}} = \frac{V_{active\ material,P_0}}{V_{active\ material,P_0} + V_{pore,P_0}} \quad (4)$$

$$\varepsilon_{s,P_1} = \frac{V_{active\ material,P_0}}{V_{electrode,P_0} - \Delta V_{pore,P_1}} = \frac{\varepsilon_{s,P_0} \cdot V_{electrode,P_0}}{V_{electrode,P_0} [1 - \varepsilon_{P_1}]} = \frac{\varepsilon_{s,P_0}}{1 - \frac{P_1}{E_{s,P_1}}} \quad (5)$$

Pressure dependency of porosity $\phi_{(P)}$

The porosity of the compressed electrode $\phi_{(P)}$ is defined as the fraction of pore volume V_{pore} , obtained by subtracting the active material volume fraction $\varepsilon_{s,(P)}$ from 1, as expressed in Equation (6).

$$\phi_{(P)} = 1 - \varepsilon_{s,(P)} = 1 - \frac{\varepsilon_{s,P_0}}{1 - \frac{P_1}{E_{s,P_1}}} \quad (6)$$

Pressure dependency of electrode single layer thickness $L_{(P)}$

Fig. 3. Schematic of porous electrode with/without external pressure.

The compressed electrode single layer thickness $L_{(P_1)}$ is determined by dividing the original electrode single layer thickness $L_{(P_0)}$ by the change in $\Delta L_{(P_1)}$, as shown in Equation (7). The value of $\Delta L_{(P_1)}$ is computed by multiplying the original electrode single layer thickness $L_{(P_0)}$ by the strain ϵ_{P_1} induced during compression.

$$L_{(P_1)} = L_{(P_0)} - \Delta L_{(P_1)} = L_{(P_0)}(1 - \epsilon_{P_1}) = L_{(P_0)} \left(1 - \frac{P_1}{E_{s,P_1}}\right) \quad (7)$$

2.2. Pressure-dependent electrochemical properties of electrodes

The Li^+ concentration $c_{(p)}$ in the negative electrode varies with pressure during battery cycling. To determine $c_{(p)}$ at different levels of external pressure, we calibrate pressure-dependent parameters in the P2D model. These pressure parameters include the negative electrode porosity ϕ_n , the positive electrode porosity ϕ_p , the separator porosity ϕ_s , the negative electrode active material diffusivity $D_{s,n}$ /conductivity $\sigma_{s,n}$, the positive electrode active material diffusivity $D_{s,p}$ /conductivity $\sigma_{s,p}$ and the electrolyte diffusivity D_e /conductivity κ_e . The active material and electrolyte diffusivity/conductivity values can be calculated from using the porosity-dependent criteria [54,60]. The equations for electrode active material diffusivity D_s , electrode active material conductivity σ_s , electrolyte diffusivity D_e , and electrolyte conductivity κ_e with the corresponding porosity ϕ are shown in Equations (8)–(11), respectively. The initial parameters $D_{s,0}$, $\sigma_{s,0}$, $D_{e,0}$, and $\kappa_{e,0}$ are derived from the P2D simulation at 0 MPa. Subsequently, we update the pressure-dependent parameters in the P2D model based on the applied external pressure and output the corresponding Li^+ concentration c in the negative electrode.

$$D_s = D_{s,0}(1 - \phi)^{\beta_s} \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma_s = \sigma_{s,0}(1 - \phi)^{\beta_s} \quad (9)$$

$$D_e = D_{e,0}\phi_s^{\beta_e} \quad (10)$$

$$\kappa_e = \kappa_{e,0}\phi_s^{\beta_e} \quad (11)$$

2.3. Model validation

2.3.1. Specimen

The study used commercial NMC 631/graphite lithium-ion prismatic cells with a nominal capacity of 75 Ah. An overview of the cell specifications is given in Table 2. The dimensions of the fresh prismatic cell are measured at 0% state of charge (SOC).

Table 2
Basic data of fresh specimen.

Parameter	Value
Nominal capacity	75 Ah
Dimension	220.6 × 105.4 × 22.8 mm
Cathode/Anode material	NMC 631/graphite
Max. Voltage	4.35 V
Min. Voltage	2.80 V

2.3.2. Experimental

In this study, an unconstrained and a constrained test setup are developed, as depicted in Fig. 4. The unconstrained setup, shown in Fig. 4(a), is designed to monitor variations in cell thickness during cycling using two high-precision capacitive sensors (Micro-Epsilon CSE3), which have an accuracy of $\pm 0.012 \mu\text{m}$ [6]. The initial distance between the sensors is recorded as a baseline, and cell thickness is determined by measuring distances d_1 and d_2 during cycling. The constrained setup, illustrated in Fig. 4(b), is designed to apply a preload force to the cell surface. This setup comprises four steel plates, designated as Top plate 1, Top plate 2, Bottom plate 1, and Bottom plate 2. The plate assembly is held together by four hexagon-nut bolts positioned at the corners. A disk spring (DIN 2093, 125 mm outer diameter, 71 mm inner diameter, 8 mm thickness) is positioned between Top plate 1 and Top plate 2 to mimic realistic bracing conditions. The disc spring used in the constrained test setup exhibits a non-linear stiffness characteristic that varies with the applied force, with an average stiffness of approximately 25 kN/mm across the operating force range. The resulting pressure variation during cycling is captured through calibration of the model against the experimentally measured force evolution, ensuring that the force-dependent spring behavior is accounted for in the simulation framework [3,5]. The battery cell is placed between Top plate 2 and Bottom plate 1, with two displacement sensors, identical to those in the unconstrained setup, mounted on the edges of Top plate 2 to track thickness changes during cycling. A 25 kN load cell (GTM Series K, accuracy class 0.02) is positioned between Bottom plate 1 and Bottom plate 2 to measure the applied force.

Four fresh cells named F01, F02, F03, and F04 are utilized in the study. The cell F01 is tested in an unconstrained condition with no applied preload force (0 kN), while cell F02, F03, and F04 are tested in a constrained condition with a preload force of 1.5 kN, 5 kN, and 15 kN, respectively. These force levels are selected to span the range of typical external loading conditions in laboratory-scale battery experiments [49]. The experimental procedure is shown in Fig. 4(c). The unconstrained test measures only cell thickness change, while the constrained test measures both cell thickness change and compression force.

Fig. 4. Schematic drawings of test setup and experimental procedure: (a) cell thickness measurement in unconstrained setup, (b) cell thickness and force measurement in constrained setup, (c) experimental procedure for unconstrained/constrained conditions.

For the unconstrained condition, the cell is cycled three times using the 1C constant current-constant voltage (CC-CV) charging protocol and 1C constant current (CC) discharging protocol, as specified in Table 3 for three times. After the charging and discharging phase, the relaxation time is set to 2 h to ensure complete electrical stabilization. The cell thickness is measured throughout the entire cycling procedure.

For the constrained condition, a preload force is applied at 30% SOC in order to represent the mechanical constraints of the battery module. After applying the preload force, the cell undergoes three cycles using 1C CC-CV charging and 1C CC discharging protocols, with a 10-min relaxation period after each charging and discharging phase to allow mechanical relaxation [45,60]. The preload force decreases during the cycling and becomes stable after three cycles. The stabilized force serves as the baseline value for subsequent measurements of cell thickness and force. In the next step, the cell is cycled three times using the same protocol, as specified in Table 3. The cell thickness and force are measured during cycling.

3. Results

3.1. Results of pressure-dependent mechanical properties of electrodes

The value of the cell compression modulus E between 0 and 1 MPa is derived from the literature [29], as shown in Fig. 5, which is reproduced from the same reference. The respective compression modulus values for the case of 0.164 MPa, 0.256 MPa and 0.612 MPa are then extracted respectively to calculate the cell strain $\epsilon_{(P)}$. These pressure case refers to the average pressure at the starting point of the discharge phase with an initial preload force of 1.5 kN, 5 kN and 15 kN respectively. The calculation results for the negative electrode active material fraction $\epsilon_{s,(P)}$, negative electrode porosity $\phi_{n,(P)}$ and the negative electrode single layer thickness $L_{(P)}$ are shown in Table 4. Each parameter is reported with decimal precision appropriate to its magnitude and physical significance. The percentage difference for each parameter is calculated relative to the baseline values at 0 MPa.

3.2. Results of pressure-dependent electrochemical properties of electrodes

Table 5 presents the pressure-dependent electrochemical parameters at 0 MPa, 0.164 MPa, 0.256 MPa and 0.612 MPa for P2D model. Each parameter uses decimal precision suited to its physical scale, with percentage differences calculated relative to the baseline values at 0 MPa. It should be noted that the Bruggeman-type relationships are valid under the assumption of a statistically homogeneous porous microstructure, where tortuosity scales with porosity through a fixed power-law exponent. The corrections are therefore applied within the validated pressure range of 0–0.612 MPa. Extrapolation beyond this range is not justified without direct experimental characterization of pressure-dependent transport properties. A bar chart is included in Appendix A to visually illustrate the pressure-dependent trends for the selected electrochemical parameters.

The detailed information on the parameters used in the P2D model is provided in Appendix A. The simulation results of the P2D model under pressure of 0.164 MPa, 0.256 MPa, and 0.612 MPa are shown in Fig. 6. The simulated voltage results under pressure of 0.164 MPa, 0.256 MPa,

Table 3
Cycling procedure specification.

Step	Control type	Control value
1	CC-CV charging	CC phase charging current 75 A, cut-off voltage 4.35 V, CV phase cut-off current 3.75 A
2	Relaxation	2 h
3	CC discharging	CC phase discharging current 75 A, cut-off voltage 2.8 V
4	Relaxation	2 h

and 0.612 MPa are illustrated in Fig. 6(a), (b), and (c), with corresponding MAPE of 0.57%, 0.30%, and 0.35%, respectively, compared to the experimental voltage. The negative electrode concentration $c_{(P)}$ during 1C discharge is shown in Fig. 6(d). At the end of discharge, the residual negative electrode concentration $c_{(P)}$ increases under higher external pressure. The detailed value of the negative electrode concentration $c_{(P)}$ at 100% SOC and 0% SOC is shown in Table 6. The percentage difference for the negative electrode concentration $c_{(P)}$ is calculated relative to the baseline values at 0 MPa. The results indicate that the discharging phase ends earlier under higher external pressure. As discussed in the literature [48,49,61], one possible reason is that the space between active material particles is compressed by the pressure, which reduces the porosity of the electrode and creates transport bottlenecks. During the discharge phase, the compressed structure impedes the extraction of Li^+ from the negative electrode. This leads to higher polarization losses and increased internal resistance, causing an earlier voltage drop and shorter discharge time. Meanwhile, the negative electrode concentration $c_{(P)}$ remains higher because the restricted pore structure prevents complete Li^+ de-intercalation, trapping Li^+ within the electrode matrix and leading to incomplete capacity utilization despite reaching the voltage cutoff.

3.3. Results of model validation

Fig. 7(a) shows the experimental thickness change under 0 MPa, 0.256 MPa, and 0.612 MPa, with the starting discharge point corresponding to the maximum negative concentration value. The equation-derived partial molar volumes $\Omega_{(c,P)}$ under pressures of 0 MPa, 0.256 MPa, and 0.612 MPa are shown in Fig. 7(b). These curves illustrate the relationship between partial molar volume $\Omega_{(c,P)}$ and Li^+ concentration in negative electrode $c_{(P)}$ across the specified pressure range. The partial molar volume curve at 0 MPa in Fig. 7(b) has been smoothed at high lithium concentration to eliminate numerical artifacts and ensure the numerical stability. Near full lithiation, the cell thickness change is relatively small, resulting in a reduced signal-to-noise ratio and increased relative measurement error, which propagates through the back-calculation procedure and amplifies sensitivity to small errors in the thickness and concentration data. Subsequently, the curves at 0 MPa, 0.256 MPa, and 0.612 MPa are used to calculate the overall variation of partial molar volume $\Omega_{(c,P)}$ with respect to concentration $c_{(P)}$ and pressure P , with validation performed using the curve at 0.164 MPa. Based on these three distinct curves, a tensor-product surface, denoted as $[T](c, P)$, is constructed using linear interpolation of least squares (LSQ) univariate splines, specifically $B_i(c)$ for concentration dependence and $B_j(P)$ for pressure dependence, as outlined in Equation (12) [62–64]. This mathematical approach creates a continuous two-dimensional surface that effectively maps the partial molar volume across a range of concentrations and pressures. The formulation of $\Omega_{(c,P)}$ is implemented as a phenomenological constitutive relation. While not derived from atomic-scale thermodynamics, the functional form is physically motivated. The concentration dependence reflects the lattice staging transitions in the host materials while the pressure dependence accounts for the mechanical work required for expansion against external constraints. Specifically, elevated compressive stress may increase the energetic penalty for lithium insertion by modulating the chemical potential and equilibrium composition of the host, effectively suppressing the macroscopic expansion response [56,65,66].

The interpolated $[T](c, P)$ surface is shown in Fig. 7(c). This provides a comprehensive visualization of the model-simulated partial molar volumes $\Omega_{(c,P)}$, highlighting its dynamic changes as a function of both pressure and negative electrode Li^+ concentration. Table 7 presents the MAPE between the surface-fitted and equation-derived partial molar volumes $\Omega_{(c,P)}$ at 0 MPa, 0.256 MPa, and 0.612 MPa, respectively. It should be noted that there is still limited understanding of how pressure affects intercalation dynamics [67]. Our calculations show that the

Fig. 5. Stiffness of cell components. This figure is reproduced from the literature [29].

Table 4
Pressure-dependent mechanical parameters under different pressure levels.

Pressure P (MPa)	Negative electrode active material fraction $\epsilon_{s,(P)}$	Negative electrode porosity $\phi_{n,(P)}$	Negative electrode single layer thickness $L_{(P)}$ (μm)
0	0.6542	0.3458	108.000
0.164	0.6602 (+0.93%)	0.3398 (-1.74%)	107.270 (-0.67%)
0.256	0.6616 (+1.12%)	0.3384 (-2.14%)	106.787 (-1.12%)
0.612	0.6648 (+1.61%)	0.3352 (-3.07%)	106.282 (-1.63%)

average partial molar volume decreases with higher pressure level. One possible reason for this is that elevated pressure compresses the structure of the host material, reducing the space available for intercalant insertion and forcing tighter packing arrangements. This structural compression may also modify the interaction between the host and intercalant species, leading to more compact configurations that minimize system volume [68–70]. Further investigations are required to elucidate the complex relationship between pressure and intercalation behavior. It is important to note that this formulation is currently validated within the experimental range of 0–0.612 MPa for the NMC631/graphite system. Application beyond this domain or to different cell chemistries would require further calibration.

The simulated change in cell thickness $dt_{(P)}$ during 1C discharge is calculated by implementing the simulated partial molar volume $\Omega_{(c,P)}$ at 0.164 MPa from $[T](c,P)$ surface into Equation (3). Fig. 7(d) presents the comparison between simulated and experimental thickness change at 0.164 MPa, yielding a MAPE of 6.87%. The starting discharge point is aligned with the maximum negative concentration value. The prediction discrepancies may be attributed to several error sources not captured by

Table 5
Pressure-dependent electrochemical parameters at 0 MPa, 0.164 MPa, 0.256 MPa and 0.612 MPa for P2D model.

Pressure P (MPa)	Negative electrode diffusivity $D_{s,n}$ [$\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$]	Positive electrode diffusivity $D_{s,p}$ [$\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$]	Negative electrode conductivity $\sigma_{s,n}$ [$\text{S}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$]	Positive electrode conductivity $\sigma_{s,p}$ [$\text{S}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$]	Electrolyte diffusivity D_e [$\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$]	Electrolyte conductivity κ_e [$\text{S}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$]
0	2.500×10^{-13}	6.700×10^{-13}	83.00	46.00	1.770×10^{-10}	0.9487
0.164	2.539×10^{-13} (+1.56%)	6.811×10^{-13} (+1.66%)	84.29 (+1.55%)	46.76 (+1.65%)	1.755×10^{-10} (-0.85%)	0.9412 (-0.79%)
0.256	2.548×10^{-13} (+1.92%)	6.842×10^{-13} (+2.12%)	84.61 (+1.94%)	46.98 (+2.13%)	1.750×10^{-10} (-1.13%)	0.9384 (-1.08%)
0.612	2.569×10^{-13} (+2.76%)	6.910×10^{-13} (+3.13%)	85.29 (+2.77%)	47.44 (+3.13%)	1.736×10^{-10} (-1.92%)	0.9309 (-1.88%)

the current model. First, minor irreversible contributions from SEI growth or gas evolution within individual discharge cycles cannot be fully excluded from the measured thickness change, despite the stabilized baseline established through pre-cycling. Second, the uniform pressure assumption of the one-dimensional P2D framework does not account for localized variations in porosity compression, Li^+ transport resistance, and partial molar volume response arising from spatial pressure heterogeneity across the prismatic cell surface [71,72]. The error between simulated and experimental thickness change at 0.164 MPa may therefore partly reflect discrepancies between spatially averaged experimental measurements and the uniform-pressure model predictions.

$$[T](c,P) = \sum_{i=0}^{n_c} \sum_{j=0}^{n_p} \alpha_{ij} B_i(c) B_j(P) \quad (12)$$

4. Conclusion

This study has developed an electrochemical-mechanical coupled swelling model for LIBs that integrates the effects of external pressure in order to predict cell thickness changes during cycling under mechanical constrained conditions. By incorporating pressure-dependent parameters into the available P2D framework, the model addresses a shortcoming of existing swelling models, which generally overlook the impact of external mechanical constraints on battery swelling behavior.

Experimental validation confirms the model's ability to predict reversible swelling behavior. For fresh NMC 631/graphite prismatic cells with a nominal capacity of 75 Ah, the equation-derived partial molar volumes at 0 MPa, 0.256 MPa, and 0.612 MPa are used to

Fig. 6. Simulated P2D results under pressure of 0.164 MPa, 0.256 MPa, and 0.612 MPa: (a) comparison of voltage under 0.164 MPa between experiment and simulation, (b) comparison of voltage under 0.256 MPa between experiment and simulation, (c) comparison of voltage under 0.612 MPa between experiment and simulation, (d) simulated negative electrode concentration $c_{(p)}$ under pressure of 0.164 MPa, 0.256 MPa, and 0.612 MPa.

Table 6

Negative electrode concentration $c_{(p)}$ at 100% SOC and 0% SOC under pressure of 0 MPa, 0.164 MPa, 0.256 MPa, and 0.612 MPa.

Pressure P (MPa)	Negative electrode concentration $c_{(p)}$ at 100% SOC ($\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	Negative electrode concentration $c_{(p)}$ at 0% SOC ($\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)
0	25119	52
0.164	25119	731 (+13.06%)
0.256	25119	1307 (+24.13%)
0.612	25119	1420 (+26.31%)

calibrate a tensor-product surface model that captures the concentration and pressure dependence. The model predicts cell thickness changes during 1C discharge with a MAPE of 6.87% compared to experimental results at 0.164 MPa. These results confirm the model's ability to capture the interactions between Li^+ concentration profiles, external pressure, and cell thickness variations. It should be noted that the model captures reversible swelling in fresh cells. The model parameters may not remain valid for aged cells where electrode microstructure and active lithiation range evolve with cycling. Extending the framework toward lifetime prediction would require integration of degradation sub-models and validation across cells at different states of health.

The model, implemented within the PyBaMM framework using pure Python code, leverages electrochemical-mechanical coupling to simulate swelling dynamics without the need for pressure and displacement sensors, making it suitable for practical applications. It accounts for variations in active material fraction, electrode porosity, and single-layer thickness under external pressure, providing a robust framework

for understanding the mechanical behavior of constrained battery modules. The current validation is specific to NMC631/graphite fresh cells under 1C discharge at controlled temperature. The primary focus of this work is the coupling of external mechanical pressure effects into the P2D framework for constrained swelling prediction, a factor not addressed in existing P2D-based studies. The integration of temperature and C-rate into the present mechanical coupling framework, alongside validation across different chemistries and operating conditions, is identified as a direction for future work.

This study enhances reversible swelling prediction models by incorporating effects of external pressure without the need for pressure and displacement sensors during operation, thereby addressing a gap in the prediction of changes in cell thickness under mechanical constraints. It highlights the importance of considering external pressure in swelling models to predict cell thickness variations in practical applications. This approach is essential for optimizing preload force in battery modules and provides a basis for future research into optimal mechanical design and real-time force monitoring, while advancing safety assessments through precise predictions of reversible swelling behavior in LIBs under mechanical constraints.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jun Yin: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Christoph Drießen:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Investigation. **Maximilian Schinagl:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Tewelde Hailay Gebregeorgis:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Mats Meussen:** Writing – review &

Fig. 7. (a) Experimental thickness change under pressure of 0 MPa, 0.164 MPa, 0.256 MPa, and 0.612 MPa, (b) equation-derived partial molar volume $\Omega_{(c,P)}$ under pressure of 0 MPa, 0.164 MPa, 0.256 MPa, and 0.612 MPa, (c) interpolated $[T](c,P)$ surface for partial molar volume, (d) comparison of simulated and experimental cell thickness change under pressure of 0.164 MPa.

Table 7

MAPE between surface-fitted and equation-derived partial molar volume $\Omega_{(c,P)}$

Pressure P (MPa)	MAPE between surface-fitted and equation-derived partial molar volume $\Omega_{(c,P)}$
0	3.18%
0.256	2.64%
0.612	1.72%

editing, Investigation. **Mesfin Haile Mamme:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Patrick Höschele:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Christian Ellersdorfer:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used DeepL, Grok 3 and Claude Sonnet 4 for checking grammar and spelling. After using these tools, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed, and

they take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. P2D model parameters and calibration results

A set of model parameters of the cell in our study is given in Table A1. These parameters are classified based on their source: (i) measured (m), obtained through experimental characterization of the cell components, (ii) calculated (c), derived from theoretical relationships or adopted from the literature, (iii) estimated (e), determined through parameter estimation algorithms during the calibration process. Parameters not explicitly listed in Table A1 are either default values or follow default equations embedded within the PyBaMM database, which were retained without modification to ensure consistency of the model implementation [30]. The layer thickness, number of layers, median particle radius, active material volume fraction and porosity are directly measured from cell disassembly analysis. The detailed cell disassembly results are listed in Appendix B. The Bruggeman coefficient is calculated based on the electrode tortuosity from cell disassembly results. The stoichiometric coefficients at 100% SOC and 0% SOC are calibrated from the half-cell potential test results listed in Appendix C. Each parameter is reported with decimal precision appropriate to its magnitude and physical significance. The remaining parameters in Table A1 are determined during a calibration process using an optimized parameterization algorithm based on the default parameters set (Chen 2020) in PyBaMM.

Table A1

Geometrical and physical parameters within the porous electrode and separator domain for the P2D model extracted at 25 °C without external mechanical pressure.

Parameters	Anode	Separator	Cathode
Layer thickness L (μm) ^m	108	10	86
Number of layers n^m	80	81	80
Median particle radius R_p (μm) ^m	5.19		2.96
Active material volume fraction ε_s^m	0.6542	0.3389	0.6967
Porosity ϕ^m	0.3458	0.6611	0.3033
Bruggeman coefficient β^c	1.70	1.23	1.82
Maximum Li concentration $c_{s,max}$ ($\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) ^e	28204		62811
Solid diffusivity D_s ($\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) ^e	2.500e-13		6.700e-13
Solid conductivity σ_s ($\text{S}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$) ^e	83.00		46.00
Electrolyte diffusivity D_e ($\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) ^e	1.770e-10	1.770e-10	1.770e-10
Electrolyte conductivity κ_e ($\text{S}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$) ^e	0.9487	0.9487	0.9487
Stoichiometric coefficients (at 100% SOC) ^c	0.8907		0.2658
Stoichiometric coefficients (at 0% SOC) ^c	0.0018		0.7365

m Measured.

c Calculated.

e Estimated.

Calibration results of P2D model during 1C discharge phase under unconstrained conditions are shown in Figure A1. Comparison of voltage between test and simulation is shown in Figure A1(a). The model shows a MAPE of 0.19% between simulated voltage and test voltage. Figure A1(b) shows the corresponding simulated negative electrode Li⁺ concentration at 1C discharge.

Fig. A1. Calibration results of unconstrained 1C discharge for P2D model: (a) comparison of voltage between experiment and simulation under pressure of 0 MPa, (b) simulated negative electrode concentration under pressure of 0 MPa.

Figure A2 illustrates the pressure-dependent trends for the selected electrochemical parameters relative to the 0 MPa baseline.

Fig. A2. Pressure-dependent electrochemical parameters at 0 MPa, 0.164 MPa, 0.256 MPa and 0.612 MPa for P2D model.

Appendix B. REM and EDX results of electrodes

Fig. B1. (a) Raster Electron Microscopy (REM) result of anode, (b) energy-Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) result of anode.

Fig. B2. (a) Raster Electron Microscopy (REM) result of cathode, (b) energy-Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) result of cathode.

Appendix C. PAT (parallel testing) - cell: Half-cell potential

Table C1
Half-cell potential for load case and the case after 30 min relaxation

SOC	Load			30 min relaxation		
	FCP (V)	HCP Anode (V)	HCP Cathode(V)	FCP (V)	HCP Anode (V)	HCP Cathode (V)
0%	2.80	0.21	3.01	3.44	0.20	3.44
20%	3.74	0.09	3.44	3.60	0.13	3.72
40%	3.81	0.08	3.81	3.66	0.12	3.78
60%	3.92	0.05	3.92	3.78	0.09	3.87
80%	4.14	0.02	4.16	3.98	0.09	4.06
100%	4.35	0.00	4.35	4.34	0.01	4.35

Symbol and description

c	concentration (mol.m ⁻³)
D	diffusion coefficient (m ² .s ⁻¹)
L	electrode layer thickness (μm)
R_p	particle radius (μm)
R	universal gas constant (8.314 J.mol ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹)
F	Faraday constant (96485 C.mol ⁻¹)
T	absolute temperature (K)
t_0^+	transference number of lithium-ion
n	number of electrode and separator layers in the pouch cell
β	Bruggeman's coefficient
i	electronic current (A)
i_0	exchange current density (A.m ⁻²)
j^{Li}	reaction current density (A.m ⁻²)
k	reaction rate (m.s ⁻¹)
ϕ	potential of phase (V)
η	electrode surface overpotential (V)
σ	solid phase conductivity (S.m ⁻¹)
κ	conductivity of electrolyte (S.m ⁻¹)
Ω	partial molar volume (m ³ .mol ⁻¹)
ϵ_s	active material volume fraction

Data availability

The datasets generated during this study are publicly available on Zenodo [<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18315429>].

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